

Evaluating Thailand's Cosmetic Surgery Tourism by Taiwanese Female Tourists

Authors : Wen-Yu Chen, Chia-Yuan Hsu, Sasinee Vongsrikul

Abstract : The present study is to explore the perception of Taiwanese females towards medical tourism in Thailand for the development of applicable marketing strategy, integrating travel motivation and cosmetic surgery trend to attract potential medical tourists from Taiwan. Since previous studies relevant to this research issue are limited, qualitative study is firstly employed by using one focus group interview and in-depth interviews with Taiwanese females. Moreover, the present research collected questionnaires from 290 Taiwanese females to provide greater understanding of research results. The top three factors that affect Taiwanese females' decision for not going to Thailand for medical tourism are "physicians and nurses cannot speak Chinese", "low quality of the cosmetic surgery product that I want to do", and "the county does not have laws to protect medical tourists' right". The finding of the empirical part would suggest the area in medical tourism industry which Thailand should promote and emphasizes in order to increase its presence as a hub for cosmetic surgery and attract Taiwanese female market. Therefore, the study contributes to the potential development of marketing strategy for medical tourism, specifically in the area of cosmetic surgery in Thailand while targeting Taiwan market.

Keywords : Thailand, Taiwanese female tourists, medical tourism, cosmetic surgery

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